

ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF SELF-ESTEEM OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18766679>

Keywords

Self-Esteem, Undergraduate students, Self value

Article History

Received: 25 December 2025

Accepted: 09 February 2026

Published: 25 February 2026

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Abstract

Background: Self-esteem is our overall sense of values, worth and abilities that influencing how we feel about ourselves and our life. Self-esteem is confidence in one's own worth and abilities himself or herself Self-esteem indicates beliefs about oneself. Self-esteem is the evaluative component of self-knowledge.

Objective: To assess the level of self-esteem of undergraduate students.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional design was used in this study. Data was collected through the structured questionnaire used to take the data from students. sections, section A sociodemographic information including age, g Marital status, residence, socioeconomic status, program, academic year and Section B including Rosenberg's Level of Self-Esteem Assessment Scale (RSES) a ten-item measure that assesses the participant's thoughts about themselves. And data were analysis using SPSS version 25 results were presented in frequencies and percentage.

Results: The findings of this study indicate that the majority of undergraduate students (83.45%) demonstrated a normal level of self-esteem, reflecting a generally healthy and balanced self-concept among most participants. This suggests that most students perceive themselves positively, recognize their self-worth, and maintain confidence in their abilities. A normal level of self-esteem is important for psychological well-being and academic success especially in demanding academic environments such as health sciences education. However, the results also revealed that 7.19% of students experienced low self-esteem. Although this percentage is relatively small, it is significant because students with low self-esteem may be more vulnerable to stress, anxiety, reduced motivation, and emotional difficulties. Such challenges can negatively influence their academic performance and overall personal development. On the other hand, 9.35% of students showed high levels of self-esteem, indicating a strong sense of self-confidence and self-worth.

Conclusion: Self-esteem is an important psychological factor that significantly influences the mental health, academic performance, and personal development of students. The study concludes that undergraduate student's majority of participants had normal level of self-esteem. While only a small minority of experience low (7.19%) and high levels (9.35 self-esteem).

Introduction

Self-esteem is our overall sense of values, worth and abilities that influencing how we feel about ourselves and our life. Self-esteem is confidence in one's own worth and abilities himself or herself, low self-esteem has a remarkable impact on mental health.¹ Self-esteem indicates beliefs about oneself. Self-important and self-knowledge are two characteristics of self-evaluation. It is best point of view how they performance, perceive and think. Self-esteem is the evaluative component of self-knowledge. There are two types of self-esteem: high self-esteem feeling positively can benefit your relationships and your overall wellbeing. Low level of self-esteem is a negative perception of one's worth, lack of confidence and negative thinking.² However, academic growth is balanced by emotional and personal development at the personal level, academic attainment are coupled with higher self-esteem. In clinical studies, students face various challenges that can impact ability to achieve self-esteem. According to Maslow, meeting basic needs: physiological care and then psychological need e.g. love.³ Students experience various forms of stress due to academic, financial and social pressures which can affect their levels of self-esteem. Medical student with low self-esteem will never grow to become a healthy, efficient doctor and suffer from anxiety and mental disturbances.⁴ Self-esteem has 2 types, specific and global. Global self-esteem is more relevant to the psychological aspect, while specific self-esteem is more relevant to behavior and is a tool for evaluating academic achievements.⁵ Literature revealed that in the incensement of self-esteem, student feel empowerment and value and it leads to positive changes such as academic progress and increased efforts for success in students. Without a certain amount of self-esteem, life can be very difficult and painful, with many basic needs not being satisfied.^{6,7} Self-esteem, is a core component

of an individual's self-concept, it identifies an individual's self-assessment of personal worth. A high self-esteem is that it provides psychological wellbeing, helping individuals to face challenges and disconnect negative emotions.⁸ Rosenberg developed the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES). RSES is the most frequently used questionnaire to assess self-reported self-esteem. RSES consists of ten items, where five are formulated positively (e.g., "I feel that I am a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.") and five negatively (e.g., "All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure."), the RSES is often modified to a Likert scale of 4 points.⁹ The current rate of suicide reflects the occurrence of mental health problems among young people. At the same time, social support and self-esteem are key factors that affect young people's mental health and suicide risk. A recent meta-analysis indicated that higher levels of social support, self-esteem and self-efficacy were significantly associated with lower risks of depression and anxiety among adolescents and young adults. Self-esteem consists of two parts: Implicit self-esteem, which is defined as a automatic, pre-conscious, emotion-related self-assessment, and Explicit self-esteem, which is rooted in rational, conscious self-assessment that may be influenced by social expectations. Sociometric theory suggests that self-esteem is part of a psychological system that stems from monitoring the interpersonal value of the self.¹⁰

MATERIAL & METHODS

This study was conducted using descriptive cross-sectional study design at people's university of medical and health sciences new campus. The duration of study was two months from 17 November to 17 January 2026 after approval of Institutional Review Board (IRB). Sample size was 278 calculated by using Rao soft sample size

Calculator, confidence level 95% and margin of error 5% sample technique was nonprobability convenience sampling method was used in study. Data was collected from undergraduate students at Peoples University of medical and health science for women Nawabshah. Data was collected through the structured questionnaire used to take the data from students. It consisted of two sections, section A sociodemographic information including age, gender, Marital status, residence, socioeconomic status, program, academic year and Section B including Rosenberg's Level of Self-Esteem Assessment Scale (RSES) a ten-item measure that assesses the participant's thoughts about themselves. The objects were scored on a

four-point scale. For questions 1,3,4,7, and 10, use a Likert scale of 3 (strongly agree) to 0 (strongly disagree). For the questions, reverse grading was done from 3 (strongly disagree) to 0 (strongly agree). The scale runs from 0 to 30. Low self-esteem is indicated by scores below 15, normal range is 15-25, and high self-esteem is shown by scores are 25-30. RSES was used for data collection participants will be require to complete the questionnaires within 10 to 15 minutes then return to the data collectors. Data analyzed by using SPSS version 25. Frequencies and percentage were calculated for categorical variables.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of Respondents

Figure 2: Academic year of the Respondents

Religion of respondent	Frequency	Percent
Muslim	255	91.7%
Hindu	23	8.3%
Total	278	100%

Table 1: Religion of Respondents

Table 2: Marital status of the Respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percent
Single	270	97.1%
Married	8	2.9%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 3: Socioeconomic status of respondents

Socioeconomic status	Frequency	Percent
Poor class	34	12.2%
Middle class	232	83.5%
High class	12	4.3%
Total	278	100%

Figure 3: Program of Respondents

Figure 4: Residence of the Respondence

Figure 5: Total level of self esteem

Table 4: Rosenberg Self Esteem Scale Items

Questionnaire	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
On the whole, I am satisfied with myself	121(43.5%)	134(48.2%)	18(6.5%)	5(1.8%)
I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	87(31.3%)	147(52.9%)	23(8.3%)	21(7.6%)
I am able to do things as well as most other people	110(39.6%)	127(45.7%)	32(11.5%)	9(3.2%)
I take a positive attitude my toward myself	99(35.6%)	126(45.3%)	35(12.6%)	18(6.5%)
I feel that I am a person of worth	105(37.8%)	136(48.9%)	26(9.4%)	11(4.0%)
At times, I think I am no good at all	31(11.2%)	87(31.3%)	113(40.6%)	47(16.9%)
I feel I do not have much too be a proud of	29(10.4%)	68(24.5%)	118(42.4%)	63(22.7%)
I wish I could have more respect for myself	60(21.6%)	92(33.1%)	70(25.2%)	56(20.1%)
All in all, I am inclined to think that I am a failure	34(12.2%)	58(20.9%)	107(38.5%)	79(28.4%)
I certainly feel useless at times,	24(8.6%)	52(18.7%)	128(46.0%)	74(26.6%)

DISCUSSIONS

This study assessed the level of self-esteem of undergraduate students at People's University of Medical and Health Sciences for Women (PUMHSW), Nawabshah the findings revealed that the majority of students (83.45%) had a normal level of self-esteem, while a smaller proportion demonstrated low (7.19%) and high (9.35%) self-esteem. These results indicate that most students possess a generally healthy self-concept; however, a meaningful minority remains psychologically vulnerable. These results are different from previous study according to research in terms of self-esteem, 68% had strong self-esteem, 30% had moderate self-esteem, and 2% had poor self-esteem the most of undergraduate students demonstrated average levels of self-esteem, suggesting that moderate self-esteem is common in health sciences students. This consistency may reflect similar academic pressures and developmental challenges experienced by students in professional health-related programs². Regarding the demographic variables this study the results concluded were as the mean age of respondents 21.59 years (SD = 1.517, Figure-1), which is higher than mean age reported in previous study, were the majority (61%) of respondents were between 19-20 years old². Figure 2 The distribution of respondents were year of study was 1st year 14. (75%), was 2nd year 16. (91%), was 3rd year 25. (90%), was 4th year 38. (49%), and 5th year was 3. (96%), academic year of respondents illustrates that students from all academic years participated in the study. This balanced representation allows comparison across different stages of undergraduate education and suggests that the findings reflect self-esteem levels across early to late academic exposure. Table 1 Religion of respondents shows that most participants were Muslim (91.7%), with a smaller proportion of Hindu students (8.3%). This reflects the religious composition of the local populations. Table 2 Marital status of respondents indicates that almost all participants were single (97.1%). This is expected in undergraduate populations and suggests that self-esteem levels observed are mainly reflective of unmarried young adults. Figure 3 Program of respondents indicates that

students were enrolled in different health science programs (BSN, DPT, Pharm-D, BSPH). The near-equal distribution across programs improves the representativeness of the sample and suggests that self-esteem issues are relevant across disciplines, not limited to a single program. Figure 4 Residence of respondents demonstrates that both urban and rural students were included, with slightly more participants from urban areas. Table 3 Socioeconomic status of respondents demonstrates that the majority of students belonged to the middle socioeconomic class (83.5%), with fewer from poor (12.2%) and high (4.3%) socioeconomic backgrounds. Socioeconomic status can influence access to resources and emotional support, which may indirectly affect self-esteem Table 4 Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale items shows that most students agreed with positive self-statements such as being satisfied with themselves and recognizing their good qualities. Conversely, a large proportion disagreed with negative statements related to feeling useless or being a failure. This pattern indicates an overall positive self-image among students. However, the proportion of students endorsing negative items highlights a subgroup experiencing self-doubt and vulnerability, emphasizing the importance of counseling services and mentorship programs. Figure 5 Total level of self-esteem reveals that the majority of respondents (83.45%) had a normal level of self-esteem, while smaller proportions had low (7.19%) and high (9.35%) self-esteem. This indicates that most students possess a generally healthy self-concept; however, the presence of low self-esteem in a minority point to the need for psychosocial supports. These results demonstrate that undergraduate students generally have normal self-esteem levels, supported by positive responses on the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale. Nevertheless, the presence of low self-esteem among a minority, combined with demographic diversity in age, program, residence, and socioeconomic status, suggests that targeted mental health and student support interventions are necessary to promote psychological well-being and academic success.

CONCLUSION

This study assessed the level of self-esteem of undergraduate students. The findings indicate that the majority of the participants demonstrate normal level of self-esteem (83.45%), smaller proportion exhibited low (7.19%) and high (9.35%) self-esteem. These results suggest that, overall undergraduate students possess a generally healthy self-concept; however, meaningful minority remains psychologically vulnerable and may benefit from targeted support. Students with low self-esteem are more likely to experience stress, reduced confidence, and emotional difficulties, which can negatively influence learning outcomes and professional development. In demanding academic environments such as health sciences education, these challenges may be further intensified. Therefore, fostering positive self-esteem is essential for promoting resilience, motivation, and effective interpersonal functioning among future healthcare professionals.

The results highlight the importance of strengthening institutional support systems. Universities should enhance access to counseling services, mentorship programs, and stress-management interventions to support students with low self-esteem. Faculty engagement, constructive feedback, and peer-support initiatives can contribute to a more supportive academic climate and promote positive self-concept. While the findings provide useful baseline evidence, the single-institution design and non-probability sampling limit generalizability. Future multi-center and longitudinal research is recommended to explore changes in self-esteem over time and to assess the effectiveness of targeted psychosocial interventions aimed at improving students' mental well-being and academic functioning.

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